

MARKETING ACTIVITIES AND COMMUNICATION POLICIES OF DAKA-TEX LLC

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7904766>

Abstract. *In this article, the main structural element of the marketing complex, the initial stage of its development is the formation and implementation of the organization's product policy, yarn products Production and packaging technologies and kalava reserves are considered.*

Keywords: *marketing, enterprise, production, yarn, knitwear, communication, market, sales.*

INTRODUCTION. The economic reforms carried out in our country open the door to wide opportunities for production enterprises. As a result of the benefits and preferences given to them, the increase of the funds at their disposal of the enterprises, the introduction of new forces and the increase of the welfare of the population serve. It is certainly gratifying to see such positive changes in our economy, in the economic activity of the country. However, today we all know well that the market economy is an economic system that operates within the framework of the influence of a complex of competition and so-called struggles. In this system, some enterprises work in cooperation with each other, while similar enterprises are in constant competition. In their economic activities, they are always up-to-date,

Each business entity develops its marketing strategy in order to ensure the continuous sale of its products. This strategy will be aimed at increasing the volume of product sales over the years, increasing the sales volume and will rely on the existing capabilities of the business entity. However, in today's fast-paced economic processes, it is time to improve this strategy. We will touch on this in more detail on the example of the general economic activity of our country.

The marketing strategy of Uzbekistan is aimed at the production of products and goods at the level of market and time demand. As we mentioned above, entrepreneurs and investors are given wide economic opportunities and tax benefits for the production of such products. In particular, enterprises operating in special industrial zones were given wide-scale tax and customs benefits and preferences for a period of 3 to 7 years depending on the volume of investments, and their connection to infrastructure facilities and communications is guaranteed. These works, of course, were one of the important factors in increasing the speed of development of developing countries, as well as

It should also be noted that the localization programs introduced by our government are implemented based on the results of marketing research, which reduces the difficulty level of occupying new markets and filling markets with new types of products. The localization program is geographically focused mainly on special economic zones. In particular, the newly established free industrial and economic zones occupy a special place in the implementation of projects aimed at modernizing the production potential, which is one of the main factors of capturing new markets of our country. It can be said that in practice it pays off.

An important part of marketing analysis is the analysis of economic and financial indicators. "Daka-Tex" LLC since it is an independent economic entity, its activity in the market

should be expressed first of all by economic indicators. Therefore, we need to analyze the financial statements in order to find out whether the management activities are organized in the enterprise.

To carry out financial and economic analysis, we first determine the ratio of separate parts of the enterprise's balance sheet. In this case, we need to consider separately the composition of assets and liabilities of the balance sheet.

Table 1

Analysis of the composition of assets of the balance sheet of "DAKA-TEX" LLC 2022

Balance sheet asset	At the beginning of the reporting year		At the end of the reporting year		Indicator of change	
	Million soums	%	Million soums	%	Million soums	%
Total assets	40,696.23	100.00%	52,815.78	100.00%	12 119.55	
1.1 Long term assets	3,952.52	9.71%	3 495.51	6.62%	-457.01	-3.09%
1.2 Current Assets	36,743.71	90.29%	49 320.27	93.38%	12,576.56	3.09%
1.2.1 Raw materials reserve	11,750.33	28.87%	14 155.52	26.80%	2 405.19	-2.07%
1.2.2 Future period expenses	0.00	0.00%	0.02	0.00%	0.02	0.00%
1.2.3 General debtors	21 332.64	52.42%	35,040.40	66.34%	13,707.76	13.93%
1.2.4 In monetary form value	3 570.74	8.77%	24,33	0.05%	-3 546.41	-8.73%

In the above tables the annual change indicators of the liabilities on the company's balance sheet are described, and we will get acquainted with the dynamics of its change below:

Table 2

Analysis of the dynamics of changes in the composition of assets of the balance sheet of "DAKA-TEX" LLC during 2018-2022

Balance sheet asset	2018 At the beginning of	2018 At the end of	2019 year At the end of	2020 year At the end of	2021 year At the end of	2022 year At the end of
	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums
Total assets	26 230.91	29 134.35	33,088.29	37,974.40	40,696.23	52,815.78
1.1 Long term assets	1 000.44	866.25	2 319.02	2 209.41	3,952.52	3 495.51
1.2 Current Assets	25 230.47	28 268.10	30,769.27	35,764.99	36,743.71	49 320.27

1.2.1 Raw materials reserve	10,861.01	14,072.09	10,626.47	13,461.32	11,750.33	14 155.52
1.2.2 Future period expenses	0.60	1 274.68	116.63	20.74	0.00	0.02
1.2.3 General debtors	10,954.55	8,728.27	19,822.14	21 156.91	21 332.64	35,040.40
1.2.4 In monetary form value	3 414.31	4 193.06	204.03	1 026.02	3 570.74	24,33

This as can be seen from the table and diagram, the total amount of assets is increasing from year to year. The fact that the amount of all types of assets on the balance sheet is increasing from year to year shows that the company is fully operating. This will stimulate the growth of the economic indicators of the enterprise and will have an effect on the stabilization of the financial situation.

Now we will analyze the liabilities of the company's balance sheet.

Table 3

Analysis of liabilities of the balance sheet of "DAKA-TEX" LLC 2022

Balance sheet is passive	At the beginning of the reporting year		At the end of the reporting year		Indicator of change	
	Million soums	%	Million soums	%	Million soums	%
Total liabilities	40,696.23	100.00%	43,650.77	100.00%	2,954.54	
1.1 On own account funds	35,075.04	86.19%	35 186.30	80.61%	111.26	-5.58%
1.2 Obligations	5 621.19	13.81%	8 464.47	19.39%	2 843.28	5.58%
1.2.1 Long term obligations	0.00	0.00%	0.00	0.00%	0.00	0.00%
1.2.2 Current obligations	5 621.19	13.81%	8 464.47	19.39%	2 843.28	5.58%

In the above tables the annual change indicators of the liabilities on the company's balance sheet are described, and we will get acquainted with the dynamics of its change below:

Table 4

Analysis of the dynamics of changes in the composition of liabilities of the balance sheet of "DAKA-TEX" LLC during 2018-2022

Balance sheet is passive	2018 At the beginning of	2018 At the end of	2019 year At the end of	2020 year At the end of	2021 year At the end of	2022 year At the end of
	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums	Million soums

Total liabilities	26 230.91	29 134.35	33,088.30	37,974.40	40,696.23	43,650.77
1.1 On own account funds	22,959.34	28,559.40	30 140.59	31 375.76	35,075.04	35 186.30
1.2 Obligations	3 271.57	574.95	2 947.71	6,598.64	5 621.19	8 464.47
1.2.1 Long term obligations	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1.2.2 Current obligations	3 271.57	574.95	2 947.71	6,598.64	5 621.19	8 464.47

And through this schedule and dynamics, we can see the absence of long-term liabilities and a significant increase in own funds in relation to current liabilities. However, it is possible to observe that the current liabilities are also increasing, albeit more slowly. It is clear that the enterprise should try to find ways to get rid of these obligations during its activity.

According to the results of the financial analysis, "DAKA-TEX" LLC pays great attention to financial strength in its activities. This can be seen from the results of the financial policy, which have been high in the last four years.

"YesAnalyzing the marketing activities of "ka-Tex" LLC, we must consider its marketing complex policy.

The main structural element of the marketing complex, the first stage of its development is the formation and implementation of the product (product) policy of the organization (enterprise).

The main products produced at "Daka-Tex" LLC:

- 1) thread
- 2) is a knitted fabric.

Ip-kalava products Production and packaging are carried out entirely on the basis of European technologies. The enterprise produces two types of yarn products, Ne 20/1 and Ne 30/1. an average of 9 tons per day, and 250-300 tons of products are produced every month. In the warehouse of the enterprisehas a large stock of kalava in its warehouse, which guarantees constant availability and uninterrupted supply to its partners. When packing yarn, 24 pieces of yarn are placed in 1 box. The weight of 1 kalava is 2 kg 150 g.

Figure 3. Yarn factory and storage warehouse

Figure 4. Thread: 34/1 (Ne 20/1)

Figure 5. Thread: Nm 50/1 (Ne 30/1)

"Daka-Tex LLC has extensive experience in the production of knitted fabric and a professional team. The knitting workshop is equipped with circular knitting machines from Pilotelli (Italy), Pailung (Taiwan) and Leadsfon (China), and flat knitting machines from Boosan (China). The presence of circular knitting machines with one and two rings allows this company to produce all types of knitted fabrics. Knitted fabrics are made of natural cotton, elastane and mixed yarns.

Figure 6. Knitting fabric production shop

Figure 7

The enterprise produces 7 types of knitted fabric: Kulirnaya glad, Interlok, Pike, Futer(loop), Futer(nachos), Ribana, Kashkorse. You can find these products below:

Figure 8. Kulirnaya glad

Kulirnaya glad- this is the thinnest of cotton knitted fabrics, it is woven from 100% cotton or with the addition of lycra. Kulirnaya glad is well stretched in the transverse direction. Knitted clothes made of it are very light and comfortable, and they are used for the production of various clothes: children's and adult underwear, T-shirts, pajamas, polo shirts, tourist clothes, special clothes, etc.

Figure 9. Interlock

The name of this knitted fabric is related to the unique weave of the thread. Translated from English, interlock means overlapping, crossing. The interlock looks the same on both sides. It is a very soft, silky and at the same time durable cotton knitted fabric, it practically does not stretch, so it is often used for sewing children's clothes and underwear. Very comfortable pajamas, nightgowns, T-shirts, etc. are made from it. Interlock is knitted on a bed of two needles fixed at a certain angle on special knitting machines.

Figure 10. Pique

Pique is a dense cotton knitted fabric, the main distinguishing feature of which is the texture of the front surface in the form of honeycomb patterns. The pique is also woven from 100% cotton and lycra. Pique is widely used in sewing popular clothes such as polo shirts.

Figure 11. Footer(loop)

Figure 12. Footer(nachos)

These knitted fabrics are named so because of a special weave, in which the lining thread is tied from the reverse side down, forming its structure, and treated with additional wool. Footer- this is an excellent heat-protecting and abrasion-resistant knitted fabric. Footer used in sewing warm products: sweaters, caps, sports suits, robes, pajamas and products for children, teenagers and adults.

Figure 13. Ribana

Ribana is a knitted fabric with a corrugated structure in small strips. Due to its elasticity, ribana is often used for cuffs and collars, and is also used in the production of children's and adult clothing. Ribana clothing absorbs moisture well and does not lose its shape. Ribana can be made of 100% cotton or with the addition of lycra, which significantly increases its elasticity.

Figure 14. Kif revealed

Kashkorse- this is a very elastic knitted fabric with a large elastic band structure. Kashkorse is made from both 100% cotton and lycra added, which increases its elasticity and makes it suitable for use in the production of clothing items such as necklines and sleeve cuffs. Kashkorse is also widely used in the production of outerwear, children's clothes, etc.

"Daka-TEX" LLC independently determines the tasks and mechanism of price policy development, the price policy development scheme based on the enterprise's development goals and objectives, organizational structure and management methods, traditions established in the enterprise, economic and financial indicators. It can be affected by such factors as the level of production costs, etc., as internal factors, and the state and development of the business environment as external factors.

"Daka-TEX" LLC One of the most advanced and largest full-cycle factories in Uzbekistan, it cooperates with large federal clothing retailers in Russia and the CIS countries. , engaged in delivery to Italy, Turkey, China and other countries.

Likewise, LLC "Daka-TEX" JSC has many years of experience on the basis of orders and has been delivering customers' orders with quality and on time. To him for many years Gloria Jeans, MODIS, Vse Mikey, Wildberries, Oodji, Detsky mir, STAN, Teximport, Coca-Cola, Vostok Servis, Ekspert Spetsodejda, Ashan, Profmax, TechnoAvia, Beeline and other companies have expressed their trust.

From the above information we can know that "Daka-TEX" LLC has also paid great attention to the marketing promotion and communication policy in relation to its customers and partners.

REFERENCES

1. Musaeva Sh.A. Marketing research. Textbook Publishing and creative department of "STAR SEL" LLC. Samarkand-2023
2. Musaeva Sh.A. Integrated marketing communication Study guide "Mahorat" publishing house, Samarkand - 2022
3. Musaeva Sh.A., Usmonova DI Innovative marketing Study guide "TURON EDITION" 2021.

4. S Musayeva WAYS TO IMPROVE DEMAND FORMATION AND SALES PROMOTION AT GOLDEN OIL LLC Science and innovation 1 (A5), 215-220
5. MS Azimovna Development of innovative marketing strategies in agriculture Web of Scientist: International Journal of Scientific Research 3 (02), 538-544
6. MS Azimovna, RN Ulugbekovna Development Conditions and Modern Trends of Business Tourism Worldwide INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY 2 (2), 63-66
7. Kotler F. i dr. Basic marketing. - M.: LLC "ID Williams", 2013.
8. MS Azimovna THE MAIN RESULTS OF THE LABOR PRODUCTIVITY OF THE STAFF OF THE HOTEL "BILLURI SITORA" LLC Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research 11(1), 348-352
9. MS Azimovna THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF MARKETING TOOLS IN INCREASING THE INTERNATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF THE TEXTILE ENTERPRISE Science and Innovation 2 (1), 47-53
10. S Musayeva MECHANISMS OF FUNCTIONING OF LOGISTIC STRUCTURES Science and innovation 2 (A2), 196-202
11. S Musayeva WAYS TO IMPROVE THE POLICY OF DISTRIBUTION OF GOODS IN FURNITURE PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES Science and innovation 2 (A2), 152-156
12. S Musayeva IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN THE NEED TO EVALUATE ENTERPRISES Science and innovation 2 (A2), 35-40
13. MS Azimovna Ways to Improve the Use of Marketing Information in the Assessment of "Stekloplastik" LLC American Journal of Economics and Business Management 5 (11), 338-343
14. MS Azimovna Efficiency of advertising activities of trading organizations and ways to increase IT Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities 12 (3), 93-97
15. Usmanov IA, Musayeva Sh.A. Features of marketing activities in the construction industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS Journal NX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal ISSN No: 2581 - 4230 VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1, Jan. -2021 <https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/view/793>
16. Usmanov IA Musaeva Sh.A. Features of marketing organization in the market of construction services. Service. Scientific journal. - Samarkand. No. 2, 2021 - pp. 86-90.
17. Usmanov IA Study of the Provision of Construction Facilities with Management Personnel. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ORANGE TECHNOLOGY. Volume: 03 Issue: 9 | Sep 2021. p.31-33 <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/2171>
18. Usmanov IA, Jumanov Sh.N. Ways to improve quality control of construction and installation works. Oriental renaissance: innovative, educational, natural and social sciences scientific journal. ISSN 2181-1784. Volume 1, Issue 10. November 2021. – P. 651-658 <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ways-to-improve-quality-control-of-construction-and-installation-works>
19. Usmanov IA Buriev HT A development strategy for the construction industry in Uzbekistan: organizational aspects of implementation. International scientific and technical journal. Real estate: economy, administration. Moscow, MGSU-No. 4 / 2021

20. Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, RESEARCH OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF S SHARQ-UNIVERSAL-SMK LLC SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 6 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
21. Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna, EXAMINATION OF THE INVESTMENT PROJECT OF LEASING COMPANIES SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 7 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337